

INNOVATIVE APPROACHES TO PERFORMING INDEPENDENT WORK OF STUDENTS OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract. *In this article, the history, development and perspective of the science of "Safety of Life Activities" and the results of socio-economic reforms in our Republic, the impact of production and territorial security problems on the safety of human life are discussed. The goal of students of a higher educational institution to study independent work, the main tasks of studying independent work, and the author proposed new approaches to organizing work with students on studying independent work topics.*

Keywords: *safety of life activities, risk, independent education, credit module, man-made, ecological, emergency situations.*

INTRODUCTION

In the current situation, issues of ensuring a safe life are one of the most urgent problems. Because , in the technosphere, the production process is broken, sanitary and hygiene norms and rules are not created for workers, the complications of unpleasant situations in the development of the environment, the occurrence of dangerous situations for human life between countries, various toxic and harmful substances and tools used by mankind cause many dangers. , threatens people's vital activities, health, environmental cleanliness, and sustainable development of the economy. For this reason, among the most important and urgent tasks of our country, the issues of ensuring the safety of the population's life have become urgent.

MAIN PART

The purpose of studying independent work is to learn the causes, characteristics, consequences of risks that arise in the life activities of future specialists and the rules for their elimination, to create safe working conditions, to protect the population from natural, man-made, ecological and other emergency situations, to protect them theoretically and practically, and is to teach the rules of first aid to the injured.

The main tasks of studying independent work: identifying and studying the risks that occur in life, creating safe working conditions in production processes, studying measures that reduce occupational diseases and prevent accidents in the technosphere . Also, to educate people with the knowledge, skills and professional qualifications to teach people how to protect themselves from natural disasters, accidents and disasters, rescue and restore citizens in affected areas, take fire safety measures, provide first aid to the injured and other important tasks. directed.

The science of life safety is divided into four sections: labor protection; civil protection, fire safety basics and medical ambulance basics are studied. State management of labor protection is carried out by the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, a specially authorized state body in the field of labor protection, as well as other state bodies that have certain powers in the field of labor protection in accordance with legislation.

The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Protection of Population and Territories

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t At the moment, in order to improve the quality of education, all HEIs have been given the right to create educational programs in the field of bachelor's and master's degrees. In the last two years, the credit module system (1 credit = 30 hours) was adopted in the educational system. In this regard, each student must receive at least 65% credits for each academic course to successfully master the subject (1800 hours in the 1st year: 30 hours/credit = 60 credits), in addition, the distribution is the number of daytime hours: 40% - classroom training and 60% independent studies of science. The analysis shows that the students' learning rate is in group a It does not exceed 30-35%, therefore, to improve the quality of education in order to master the subject and gain independent thinking, the main attention should be paid to independent work with students.

According to the curriculum of the Academy of Labor and Social Relations in the section of directions, from the subject of life activity safety **61020100** - Life activity safety, **61020200** - Labor protection and technical safety (by sectors) A total of **360 hours** are allocated to each course of which **150 hours are classroom** (60 hours of lectures, 60 hours of practice, 30 hours of seminars) and **210 hours** of independent training.

m In other areas of the Academy **60411200** - Management (by industries and sectors) and **60411400** - Human resource management total, **120 hours**; out of that, **60 hours of lectures** (30 hours of lectures, 30 hours of practical) and **60 hours of independent education** are allocated.

e The procedure for performing independent work is carried out in the following sequential steps:

1. Basic concepts on the subject.

2. Relevance of the topic (*what are the problems with the topic?*).

3. The results achieved by the topic (*What was learned in connection with the completion of the topic?*)

4. Implementation of the topic in practice (*Where can it be implemented?*)

e We will consider **the importance of studying the science of " Safety of life activities" and the scientists who contributed to the study** according to the order of independent work .

c **Topic: The importance of studying the science of "Safety of life activities" and scientists who contributed to the study.**

The purpose of the work: to study the importance of learning the science of "Safety of life Activities" and the relationship of other sciences in learning.

i The student independently prepares a 20-minute lecture on this topic. He covers the lecture in the form of a presentation in the form of a seminar-training.

u Instructions for conducting independent study.

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Plan:

1. Explain the relevance of studying the science of "life safety".
2. To provide information about world scientists and scientists of our country who made a great contribution to the study of HFX problems.
3. Proposals and recommendations for the wide promotion of the study of the science of "life safety".

Based on these plans, the student prepares a presentation for the lecture. If the student has additional ideas and information, he can change the plan without leaving the topic.

The student uses the recommended literature to cover the topic. In addition, additional literature on the topic can be used and they will be included in the list of used literature.

THEORETICAL INFORMATION ON THE SUBJECT OF INDEPENDENT WORK

In the current era, people are full of various dangers, and at the same time, we are living in a time when science and technology are developing, and human living conditions are improving more and more. At the same time, the number of various accidents, disasters, various disasters, and terrorist acts that threaten human life is increasing. The saddest thing is that in addition to material and moral damage, the number of people killed in these emergency situations is increasing.

According to the World Statistics Office, 10 million people died in the First World War, 60 million people died in the Second World War , and three times more people died from man-made disasters between 1945 and 2000 (Figure 1).

Figure 1. A comparison diagram of the death toll from man-made disasters between the two world wars, 1945-2000 .

Geographically, the Republic of Uzbekistan is located in such a region that some whims of nature have not bypassed the territory of the republic.

Natural disasters are a factor that imposes heavy burdens on people, causing incomparable damage to the ecological environment, economic objects, and they occur every year in different regions of our Republic. For example: in the mountainous regions of our republic (Tashkent, Kashkadarya, Namangan, Fergana, Samarkand, Surkhandarya, Jizzakh) in early spring, emergency situations related to floods, landslides and landslides are among them. Also, in the desert zones of our Republic, including: Kashkadarya, Surkhandarya, Bukhara, Navoi, Khorezm regions, and in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, strong dust and pollen are affecting the health of citizens and the economy of our country.

If we analyze the causes of emergency situations, we can see that about 80% of them are related to human activity. More than 40 percent of the victims die due to their inability to correctly

assess the conditions of natural and man-made emergency situations, especially due to their inability to find the right ways to move in these conditions.

World experience shows that one of the main ways to reduce the number of victims is to teach all categories of the population, including young people, how to move properly in emergency situations. In our opinion, such training should be carried out in a permanent, regular, continuous manner in the family, in the neighborhood, in pre-school educational institutions and in general secondary schools and institutions of higher education.

In 1991, under the motto "Life is safe", it was shown and emphasized that the World Congress should be held and special attention should be paid to the solution of the issues discussed in it. The subject "Safety of life activities" has been included in the curricula of all bachelor's programs.

Relevance of the science: It covers the development and prospects of the science of life activity safety (HFX) and the results of socio-economic reforms in our Republic, the impact of production and territorial security problems on the safety of human life. Because in the current situation, issues of ensuring a safe life are one of the most urgent problems. Because the disruption of the production process in the technosphere, the failure to create sanitary and hygiene norms and rules for workers, the complication of unpleasant situations in the development of the environment, the occurrence of situations that endanger human life between countries, the use of various toxic and harmful substances and tools by mankind have created many dangers. threatens people's vital activities, health, environmental cleanliness, and sustainable development of the economy. For this reason, among the most important and urgent tasks of our country, the issues of ensuring the safety of the population's life have become urgent. The science of "Safety of life activity" studies the solution of these problems.

In 2020, 11,621 violations of labor protection legislation were detected at industrial enterprises in Uzbekistan, and 607 accidents occurred. As a result, 693 employees were injured, 201 of them died. In 2021, 19,967 violations of labor protection laws, 810 accidents resulted in 907 injuries, 238 deaths, 632 serious injuries, and 37 minor injuries in industrial enterprises. As the year passes, the increase in risks requires an increase in knowledge on the safety of life activities. When labor protection and technical safety regulations are allowed to be violated, or when the integrity of management control is neglected, the number of accidents in production enterprises has been observed to increase.

In the case of the Republic, it is clear from the analysis that if an accident occurs, along with the cessation of income, a large amount of material damage and loss of life of workers directly related to the enterprise, pollution of the environment has been proven.

Studying the science of life safety allows not only when risks arise in the technosphere, but also to reduce the incidence of occupational diseases of workers, to prevent accidents, as well as to reduce the scale of human death and material damage in emergency situations that occur in the biosphere (environment).

2. Humanity has always paid special attention to creating safe living and working conditions. The subject was first studied scientifically by the Greek philosophers Aristotle (387-322 AD) and Hippocrates (459-377 AD). Hippocrates wrote about the harmful effects of ore dust on human health. For the first time, he compiled a list of harmful deeds. Described the harmful aspects of working with lead. Later, another scientist, Golen, created a work in which the

pathological conditions caused by the harmful effects of lead dust were described in detail. In the 1st century BC, Katta Plini studied the harm of the dust raised during sulfur mining.

In the 15th-16th centuries, as a result of the rapid development of the field of mining and metallurgy, there was an increase in scientific works on occupational diseases caused by harsh working conditions and dust in mining. These are the works of Agricola and Paracelsus.

The actions of the great scientists of the ancient and medieval ages laid the foundation for the emergence of a separate science that studies the origin of diseases related to professional activity. The founder of the science is Bernardino Ramasini (1633-1714), an Italian doctor, professor, rector of Paduan University. His book "Thoughts on diseases of artisans" is a fundamental work, which systematically analyzes the problems of occupational hygiene in various fields and presents the clinical definition of diseases related to occupations.

Russian scientist MVLomonosov (1711-1765) on labor protection in mining, FFYerismanov (1842-115) on labor hygiene in his works entitled "Physical and Mental Labor Hygiene" addressed this issue in detail. Among the Russian scientists, our contemporaries, NDZolotnitsky, NVSolovyov, DAKelbert, VLGintillo, MIGrimitlin made a great contribution to life safety and labor protection.

In the life process, the interaction of a person with the environment and its constituents in accordance with YNKurjakovskiy's law of preservation of life, which states that "Life cannot exist only in the process of movement of substances, energies and information flows through a living body" based on Currents in the law of life preservation are necessary for a person to satisfy his needs for food, water, air, solar energy, and information about the surrounding environment.

Our great grandfathers - Abu Rayhan Beruni, Abu Ali ibn Sina, Zahridin Muhammad Babur and MNNabiev, TIIskandarov, and others made great contributions to the development of life safety and labor protection.

Scientific and technical progress in life activities is bringing drastic innovations to the field of production. In the process, the form of labor tools and subject is changing. This, in turn, affects working conditions.

There are several stages of development and formation of labor protection in occupational safety, and they are as follows:

Phase 1 - began in early 1900 (1903) with the adoption of a program containing the following provisions:

- introduction of an 8-hour working day;
- one day off per week;
- Prohibition of child labor under the age of 15;
- elimination of women's work in industries harmful to health;
- rest on holidays;
- liability of the factory in case of injury to employees;
- providing free medical care;
- preservation of salary in case of illness.

Due to the revolution in 1917, the mentioned regulations were implemented, and also forced the manufacturers of other countries to improve the working conditions in terms of safety of operation.

Step 2 – putting the rules into practice.

The following obvious examples can be given to this stage:

11.11.17 - Decree on 8-hour working day and 48-hour working week was adopted.

At that time, the following were installed:

- breaks during work;
- reduction of working week in harmful working conditions;
- Prohibition of women's and teenagers' work in underground and out-of-hours jobs;
- introduction of a 6-hour working day for teenagers.

18.05.18 - Labor inspection was established (on ensuring labor safety).

1918 The Code of Labor Laws (KZOT) was adopted.

Stage 3 - harmful factors in production were studied and recommendations were sought to eliminate the harmful effects.

1929 - A scientific research institute for the study of occupational diseases was established.

1932 - The list of special heavy and harmful works was approved.

The 4th stage is the stage of improvement of working conditions in terms of operational safety, inclusion of labor protection measures in the plans of organizations (late 50s).

Stage 5 – Modern (today).

Protection of life and health of employees is provided by the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Labor Code, "On Labor Protection", "On Trade Unions", "On Radiation Safety", "On Protection of the Population from Natural, Man-made and Environmentally Dangerous Events", "On industrial safety of hazardous production facilities", "On technical regulation", "On social protection of disabled people in the Republic of Uzbekistan", "On mandatory civil liability insurance of the employer", "On conformity assessment" of Uzbekistan. It is guaranteed by the Laws of the Republic, as well as by-laws, sanitary rules and norms, regulatory documents in the field of technical regulation on labor protection issues, and other documents.

3. The safety of life activities serves the following tasks:

1. Helps ensure the safety of the population;
2. They help citizens to maintain their health and avoid occupational diseases;
3. Increases the useful work coefficient of employees.

Risks are both latent (potential) and real. 500 million in the world. 1/5 of them were disabled as a result of an accident. 19 million annually in the CIS countries. people would be injured, about 500,000 of them would die, 50-60,000 of them as a result of road traffic, 10,000 from fire, 14,000 in production. Every year in the CIS countries, as a result of various accidents, about 30,000 people become disabled. Statistics show that injuries worldwide have increased from 4 to 19 (percent) (Table 1).

Table 1.

Average injuries per year (percentage)

States	Russia	in Western Europe	In Eastern Europe
total	2	8	12
As a result of an accident	1.5	0.5	0.8
in percent	13.6	6.25	6.6

Any activity is hidden (potentially) dangerous. Risk level - the risk is manageable. Risk - brings risk to the main idea (concept). This idea is based on the fact that security cannot be completely lost. Safety is a state of operation in which risks are excluded based on certain

assumptions. Safety is the means, guidelines, manuals, and methods used to achieve this goal, if the goal is the safety of life activities . XFX is a science that teaches you how to study and protect against risks.

In our republic, if the science of life activity safety is taught in the form of games in the form of games to primary school students in physical education and education classes, and to high school students and vocational education students as practical training, knowledge and skills on safety would be formed among the lower population today (Table 2).).

As a result, risks are avoided, damages and losses are reduced in production and non-production activities, overtime, on vacation and in our general activities. Workers, engineers-builders, who are well aware of the safety of activity, operate on the basis of standard regulatory requirements, and ensure the seismic tolerance and safety of the buildings and structures built by them. Therefore, if every citizen of our country learns the science of life safety from childhood and develops knowledge and skills about the science, the more safety conditions will be provided.

Table 2.

Recommendations for promoting the study of the science of "life safety".

No	Type of education	Hours per week	Type of training
1.	Preschool educational institution	2 hours	In game view
2.	Primary education	2 hours	in physical education and training classes,
3.	Middle school classes (grades 5-8)	3 hours	Special hours in education class
4.	Vocational education students	4 hours	Life activity safety practical lessons
5	In a higher education institution	4 hours	Theoretical and practical science of life safety for all directions.

The science of life safety is also used in production and non-production at work, at home, on vacation. Science is applied to our daily activities to ensure our safety, health and productivity in every situation .

The performance of independent work is evaluated based on the following criteria.

Evaluation criteria

"5" if the topic fully incorporates its content based on the plan;

"4" if the subject is partially embodied on the basis of the plan;

"3" if he partially embodied the subject plan and did not use internet materials;

A grade of "2" is assigned to a student who does not incorporate the content of the subject .

CONCLUSION

Currently, in most HEIs, the study of topics for independent work is not given enough attention, often limited to a list of these topics and formal supervision.

We, as authors, offer a new approach to organizing work with students on the study of independent work topics.

To do this, we suggest doing the following:

1. Classify all topics covered by difficulty:

- Type 1 is simple;

- 2nd category medium;
 - Category 3 complex.
2. Category 3 topics should be passed as an audience hour. Because this category of topics is difficult for students.
 3. Subjects of students' independent work should ensure the continuity of the development of the subject, for example, after each audience lecture there should be a topic for independent work. With this distribution of topics, it is easy for the teacher to control the mastery of the topic by students.
 4. It is appropriate to use this educational technology in practical and seminar classes. The traditional "question-and-answer" method should be abandoned in the lessons, and students should be given freedom of thought, that is, students will be free to ask questions to students and express their opinions. By conducting such practical activities, we teach the student to think, to express his opinion and suggestions. At the end of the lesson, the teacher summarizes the results and assigns grades.
 5. It is necessary to develop a criterion for assessing knowledge (on credit module) on issues of personnel training.
 6. It is necessary to develop criteria for monitoring students' knowledge of independent work topics.
 7. The authors aim to improve the quality of education by paying special attention to the independent work of students, and we use the science of life safety as an example.

REFERENCES

1. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. Buyuk kelajagimizni mard va olijanob xalqimiz bilan birga quramiz. 2017.
2. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. Qonun ustuvorligi va inson manfaatlarini ta'minlash – yurt taraqqiyoti va xalq farovonligining garovi. 2017.
3. Mehnatni muhofaza qilish to'g'risida: O'zbekiston Respublikasining qonuni (yangi tahriri). 2016-yil 22 sentabr. O'RQ-410-son-URL: <https://www.lex.uz/acts/-3031427>. (24.12.2016).
4. O'zbekiston Respublikasining Mehnat kodeksi. 1995-yil 21-dekabr. – URL: <https://lex.uz/docs/-142859>. (04.12.2020).
5. Yuldashev O.R., Nurmamatova R.R. Mehnat muhofazasi. Darslik.-T.: FVV Akademiyasi, 2021. - 699 b.
6. Yuldashev O.R., Nurmamatova R.R. Hayot faoliyati xavfsizligi. Darslik.-T.: "Complex print", 2020. 672 b.
7. Nurmamatova R.R. Hayot faoliyati xavfsizligi. O'quv qo'llanma.-T.: Qarshi DU bosmaxonasi, 2019. 278 b.
8. F.R. Valiyeva, Abdunazarova Nargiza Fatxullayevna, Zakirov Alisher Akbarovich The importance of ensuring the mental, physical, spiritual, spiritual development of educators of pre-school educational organizations.//Босма //Turkish Online Journal of Qualitative Inquiry (TOJQI) Volume 12, Issue 8. July. 2021:6919.
9. www.lex.uz - O'zR Adliya vazirligi sayti.
10. www.bilim.uz - O'zR Oliy va o'rta maxsus ta'lim vazirligi sayti.
11. www.mintrud.uz – O'zR Mehnat vazirligi sayti.
12. <http://www.hse.gov.uk/toolbox/introduction.htm>
13. <https://www.healthandsafetyatwork.com/>

14. www.healthyworkinglives.com/
15. www.safetyrisk.net/free-safety-ebooks/
16. Uzbekistan Republic of Labor protection and safety about regulatory and legal documents collection , Tashkent " Akademnashr " 2018, N. Karimova , page 21.